

1 ***Salinivibrio kushneri* sp. nov., a moderately halophilic bacterium**
2 **isolated from salterns**

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15

16 **Running title:** *Salinivibrio kushneri* sp. nov.

17

18 *Abbreviations:* MLSA, Multilocus Sequence Analysis; ANI, Average Nucleotide
19 Identity, DDH, DNA-DNA hybridization; GGDC, Genome-to-Genome Distance
20 Calculator.

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26 **Abstract**

27 Ten Gram-stain-negative, facultatively anaerobic, moderately halophilic bacterial
28 strains, designated AL184^T, IB560, IB563, IC202, IC317, MA421, ML277, ML318,
29 ML328A and ML331, were isolated from water ponds of five salterns located in Spain.
30 The cells were motile, curved rods and oxidase and catalase positive. All of them grew
31 optimally at 37 °C, at pH 7.2-7.4 and in the presence of 7.5 % (w/v) NaCl. Based on
32 phylogenetic analyses of the 16S rRNA, the isolates were most closely related to
33 *Salinivibrio sharmensis* DSM 18182^T (99.6-98.2 % 16S rRNA gene sequence
34 similarity) and *Salinivibrio costicola* subsp. *costicola* DSM 11403^T (99.0-98.1 %).
35 According to the MLSA analyses based on four (*gyrB*, *recA*, *rpoA* and *rpoD*) and eight
36 (*ftsZ*, *gapA*, *gyrB*, *mreB*, *pyrH*, *recA*, *rpoA* and *topA*) concatenated gene sequences, the
37 most closely relatives were *S. siamensis* JCM 14472^T (96.8-95.4 % and 94.9-94.7 %,
38 respectively) and *S. sharmensis* DSM 18182^T (94.0-92.6 % and 92.9-92.7 %,
39 respectively). *In silico* DNA-DNA hybridization (GGDC) and Average Nucleotide
40 Identity (ANI) showed values of 80-100 % and 97.7-100 %, respectively with the
41 related species demonstrating that the ten isolates constituted a single novel species of
42 the genus *Salinivibrio*. Its pangenome and core genome consist of 6,041 and 1,230
43 genes, respectively. The phylogeny based on the concatenated orthologous core genes
44 revealed that the ten strains form a coherent phylogroup well separated from the rest of
45 the species of the genus *Salinivibrio*. The major cellular fatty acids of strain AL184^T
46 were C_{16:0} and C_{18:1}. The DNA G+C content range was 51.9-52.5 mol% (*T_m*) and 50.2-
47 50.9 mol% (genome). Based on the phylogenetic-phylogenomic, phenotypic and
48 chemotaxonomic data, the ten isolates represent a novel species of the genus
49 *Salinivibrio*, for which the name *Salinivibrio kushneri* sp. nov. is proposed. The type
50 strain is AL184^T (= CECT 9177^T = LMG 29817^T).

51

52 **Keywords:** *Vibrionaceae*, *Salinivibrio*, moderately halophilic bacteria, new species,
53 salterns, genomic analysis.

54

55 **Introduction**

56 In 1938 Smith [44] described the species *Vibrio costicolus* isolated from rib
57 bones of bacon. This species was one of the few moderately halophilic bacteria included
58 on the Approved Lists of Bacterial Names [43], correctly named as *V. costicola*. Early
59 studies on water of ponds from marine salterns showed that halophilic vibrios were
60 easily isolated [50] and lately they were characterized taxonomically as members of *V.*
61 *costicola* [11,14], permitting an amended description of this species. This bacterium has
62 been used as a model microorganism for many physiological studies [19,22,33,49], due
63 to the fact that it is able to grow over a wide range of salt concentrations. In 1996
64 Mellado et al. [31] proposed a reclassification of *V. costicola* into a new genus, named
65 as *Salinivibrio costicola*, on the basis of the 16S rRNA gene sequence comparison,
66 showing that it constitutes a separate phylogenetic clade with respect to the genus
67 *Vibrio*, as well as on the phenotypic differences with the most closely related taxa. This
68 genus belongs to the family *Vibrionaceae* within the class *Gammaproteobacteria* and
69 includes Gram-stain-negative, curved motile rods, facultatively anaerobic, able to grow
70 on a NaCl range from 0.5 to 20 % (w/v), and catalase and oxidase positive. The DNA
71 G+C content ranges from 49.0 to 51.0 mol% [16,31]. Currently, the genus *Salinivibrio*
72 comprises four species, one of them with three subspecies: *Salinivibrio costicola* subsp.
73 *costicola* [11,16,31,44], *Salinivibrio costicola* subsp. *vallismortis* [18], *Salinivibrio*
74 *costicola* subsp. *alcaliphilus* [38], *Salinivibrio proteolyticus* [2], *Salinivibrio siamensis*

75 [5] and *Salinivibrio sharmensis* [39]. Members of this genus inhabit salted meats, brines
76 and hypersaline environments.

77 The evolutionary history of several vibrios (including the type species of the
78 genus *Salinivibrio*) was reconstructed in 2007 by means of multilocus sequence analysis
79 (MLSA) of nine genes (*ftsZ*, *gapA*, *gyrB*, *mreB*, *pyrH*, *recA*, *rpoA*, *topA* and 16S
80 rRNA), proposing the *Salinivibrio* clade [41]. Later in 2013, the vibrio clades were
81 updated by MLSA based on the eight protein-coding housekeeping genes previously
82 mentioned, delineating a super-clade grouping the genera *Salinivibrio*, *Grimontia* and
83 *Enterovibrio* [42]. Recently, López-Hermoso et al. [27] carried out a study in which 70
84 new isolates belonging to the genus *Salinivibrio* and the type strains of the species and
85 subspecies of this genus were analyzed by 16S rRNA gene sequence comparison and
86 MLSA. The data showed that the 16S rRNA gene was not able to properly differentiate
87 the new isolates or assign them to the previously described species of *Salinivibrio* but
88 alternative MLSA analyses allowed to clearly distinguish well-defined phylogroups.
89 They validated the MLSA, based on the concatenation of *gyrB*, *recA*, *rpoA* and *rpoD*
90 housekeeping genes, in order to replace the DNA-DNA hybridization (DDH) assays in
91 the genus *Salinivibrio*, establishing a cut-off value for species delineation of 97 %
92 concatenated MLSA similarity. Besides, in this study they observed clearly that some of
93 the isolates (which formed a single phylogroup) could constitute a new species within
94 this genus.

95 In this study, we carried out the taxonomic characterization of ten moderately
96 halophilic bacteria from five salterns located in different places in Spain selected from
97 the previous study of López-Hermoso et al. [27], and the data suggest that they
98 constitute a novel species of the genus *Salinivibrio*. Their characterization was achieved
99 by following a polyphasic approach. The phylogenetic, genotypic and phenotypic

100 characteristics of these strains, including 16S rRNA gene sequence analysis, MLSA,
101 DDH, ANI, GGDC and chemotaxonomic features, have been carried out in order to
102 define their taxonomic status.

103 **Materials and methods**

104 *Bacterial strains and growth conditions*

105 The strains used for this study were isolated from water samples collected from
106 different ponds of salterns of Spain: strain AL184^T was isolated from Santa Pola,
107 Alicante, strains IB560 and IB563 from Isla Bacuta, Huelva, strains IC202 and IC317
108 from Isla Cristina, Huelva, strain MA421 from La Malahá, Granada, and strains
109 ML277, ML318, ML328A and ML331 were isolated from Es Trenc, Mallorca. The
110 salinity of the samples was determined to be between 5 and 21 % salts [27]. The strains
111 were isolated by plating 0.1 ml of the water samples on SW medium with the pH
112 adjusted between 7.2-7.4 with 1 M KOH and incubated at 37 °C. After isolation, the
113 strains were subsequently purified three times by plating on the same medium. The
114 composition of SW medium is the following: (g l⁻¹): NaCl, 58.5; MgCl₂·6H₂O, 9.75;
115 MgSO₄·7H₂O, 15.25; CaCl₂, 0.25; KCl, 1.5; NaHCO₃, 0.05; NaBr, 0.175; and yeast
116 extract, 5.0, and solidified with 1.8 % (w/v) agar when necessary. The strains were
117 routinely grown on SW medium and were maintained on the same medium in slant
118 tubes, and for long term preservation at -80 °C in SW broth with 20 % (v/v) glycerol. *S.*
119 *costicola* subsp. *costicola* DSM 11403^T, *S. costicola* subsp. *alcaliphilus* DSM 16359^T,
120 *S. costicola* subsp. *vallismortis* DSM 8285^T, *S. proteolyticus* DSM 19052^T, *S.*
121 *sharmensis* DSM 18182^T and *S. siamensis* JCM 14472^T were used as reference strains
122 for comparison purposes in the present study (Supplementary Table S1).

123 *Phenotypic characterization*

124 Cell morphology and motility were examined by phase-contrast microscopy
125 (Olympus CX41) from exponentially growing cultures. The morphology and
126 pigmentation of colonies were observed on SW solid medium after 24 h of incubation at
127 37 °C. Growth range and optimum were determined on SW medium with different salt
128 concentrations (0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5, 15, 17.5, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24 and 25%, w/v)
129 at pH 7.2-7.4. To determine the optimal and range of temperature and pH supporting the
130 growth of the strains, SW broth cultures were incubated at 5-35°C at intervals of 5 °C
131 and from 35-50 °C in increments of 1 °C and at pH 4-10 at intervals of 0.5 pH units with
132 the addition of the appropriate buffering capacity to each medium [40]. Growth was
133 determined by monitoring the optical density at 600 nm using a spectrophotometer.
134 Catalase activity was determined by bubble production in 3 % (w/v) H₂O₂ solution.
135 Oxidase activity was examined using 1 % (v/v) tetramethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine [21].
136 Hydrolysis of aesculin, casein, DNA, gelatin, starch and Tween 80, Voges-Proskauer
137 and methyl red tests, production of indole, phenylalanine deaminase, phosphatase,
138 nitrate and nitrite reduction and Simmon's citrate were determined as described by
139 Cowan and Steel [6] with the addition of 7.5 % total salts to the medium [36,50].
140 Growth under anaerobic conditions (with H₂/CO₂) was determined by incubation in an
141 anaerobic jar using Anaerogen (Oxoid) to generate an anaerobic atmosphere, and an
142 anaerobic indicator (Oxoid), on SW solid medium during one week. Acid production
143 from carbohydrates was determined using a phenol red base supplemented with 1 %
144 carbohydrate and SW medium; this medium was a modification of the original
145 described elsewhere [50]. For determination of the range of substrates used as carbon
146 and energy sources or as carbon, nitrogen and energy sources, the classical medium of
147 Koser [20] as modified by Ventosa et al. [50] was used. This medium contained (per
148 liter): 75 g NaCl, 2 g KCl, 0.2 g MgSO₄·7 H₂O, 1 g KNO₃, 1 g (NH₄)₂HPO₄, 0.5 g

149 KH_2PO_4 and 0.05 g yeast extract (BD). Substrates were added as filter-sterilized
150 solutions to give a final concentration of 1 g l⁻¹, except for carbohydrates, which were
151 used at 2 g l⁻¹.

152 *Phylogenetic analysis*

153 The almost-complete 16S rRNA gene and four protein-coding housekeeping
154 genes were previously sequenced and analyzed by López-Hermoso et al. [27]. The
155 almost-complete 16S rRNA gene sequence of strains AL184^T, IB560, IB563, IC202,
156 IC317, MA421, ML277, ML318, ML328A and ML331 had a length of 1435, 1468,
157 1467, 1478, 1435, 1480, 1483, 1479, 1431 and 1445 bp, respectively; whereas
158 housekeeping genes had a length: *gyrB* (623 bp), *recA* (701 bp), *rpoA* (820 bp) and
159 *rpoD* (734 bp) [27]. The sequences obtained from the 16S rRNA gene and the four
160 housekeeping genes were assembled by using ChromasPro software (Technelysium Pty)
161 and edited to solve ambiguous positions. Multiple sequence alignments were made
162 using CLUSTAL_X 2.1 [23] and corrected by visual inspection using BioEdit [15]
163 taking into account the corresponding amino acid alignments for protein-coding genes.
164 Phylogenetic trees were constructed using MEGA 5 [47] for neighbour-joining and
165 maximum-parsimony methods and PhyML [13] for the maximum-likelihood (ML) [9]
166 method. Neighbour-joining analyses were performed using Jukes-Cantor parameter
167 model [18]. Maximum-parsimony analyses were carried out using a heuristic search
168 option. For ML analysis, the GTR model was selected and the base frequencies, the rate
169 matrix, the proportion of invariable sites and the gamma distribution were estimated via
170 likelihood. Bootstrap analyses were based on 1000 replications [10]. The sequence
171 accession numbers used in this study are shown in Supplementary Table S1.
172 Additionally, an eight gene (*ftsZ*, *gapA*, *gyrB*, *mreB*, *pyrH*, *recA*, *rpoA* and *topA*) MLSA
173 was also carried out as previously described [1,41,42], retrieving the housekeeping

174 genes from the available genomes [26], using the methodology indicated above for
175 sequence alignment and tree construction.

176 *DNA G+C content and DNA–DNA hybridization*

177 The G+C content of the genomic DNA of the ten strains was determined from
178 the midpoint value (T_m) of the thermal denaturation profile [29] by using the equation of
179 Owen and Hill [34], obtained with a Perkin-Elmer UV-Vis Lambda 20
180 spectrophotometer at 260 nm equipped with a PTP-1 peltier system programmed with
181 an increasing temperature of 1 °C min⁻¹. DNA–DNA hybridization studies were
182 performed using the competition procedure of the membrane method [17], as described
183 in detail by Arahal et al. [3,4]. The hybridization temperature was 52.2 °C, and the
184 percentage of hybridization was calculated according to Johnson [17]. The experiments
185 were carried out in triplicate and the percentages shown are the mean values. Besides,
186 the genomic G+C content calculation based on the draft genome sequences was
187 performed with the tool enveomics [28].

188 *Chemotaxonomic analysis*

189 The fatty acid composition was determined for cells of strain AL184^T, selected
190 as representative of this bacterial group, grown for 24 h at 35 °C in the medium 1
191 described by Romano et al. [39] containing (g l⁻¹): yeast extract, 10.0; NaCl, 100.0;
192 Na₃-citrate, 3.0; Na₂CO₃ 3.0, KCl, 2.0; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 1.0; MnCl₂·4H₂O, 0.00036;
193 FeSO₄, 0.05. The resulting pH was 9.0. The fatty acid profile was obtained with an
194 Agilent 6850 gas chromatograph using the database TSBA6 (MIDI, 2008) [32]. These
195 analyses were carried out at the Spanish Type Culture Collection (CECT), Valencia,
196 Spain.

197 *Genome sequencing, assembly and annotation*

198 Draft genomes of the ten isolates and the type strains of the species and
199 subspecies of *Salinivibrio* were previously sequenced by López-Hermoso et al. [26]. We
200 also used the draft genome sequence of *Salinivibrio costicola* subsp. *costicola* LMG
201 11651^T as described by Gorriti et al. [12]. The accession numbers of the draft genome
202 sequences used in this study are shown in Supplementary Table S1.

203 *Calculation of in silico DDH and ANI values*

204 *In silico* DDH was calculated by the Genome-to-Genome Distance Calculator
205 (GGDC 2.0) using the BLAST+ method [30]. Results were based on recommended
206 formula 2 (identities/HSP length), which is independent of genome length and is thus
207 robust against the use of incomplete draft genomes. Calculation of the average
208 nucleotide identity (ANI) from the draft genome sequences used previously for *in silico*
209 DDH was performed with JSpecies [37], whereas OrthoANI percentages were
210 calculated as described by Lee et al. [24].

211 *Core genome phylogenetic reconstruction*

212 All predicted protein-coding genes and amino acids annotated from each
213 available genome were compared using an all-versus-all BLAST search [28]. This
214 analysis identified shared reciprocal best matches (defined as > 70 % nucleotide identity
215 or > 40 % amino acid identity) in all pairwise genome comparisons (core orthologues)
216 of the ten *Salinivibrio* strains and the related taxa of the genus *Salinivibrio*, as well as
217 the reference strain *Vibrio cholerae* N16961. The core orthologous genes were
218 individually aligned using MUSCLE [8]. The resulting nucleotide alignments were
219 concatenated to create a core-genome alignment, and the phylogenomic tree was
220 reconstructed by neighbour-joining method with MEGA 5 [47]. Additionally, the core

221 orthologous and unique proteins were used to construct a Venn diagram with the
222 VennPainter tool [25].

223 **Results and discussion**

224 *Phenotypic characterization*

225 Cells of the ten new isolates AL184^T, IB560, IB563, IC202, IC317, MA421,
226 ML277, ML318, ML328A and ML331 were motile, slightly curved rods, Gram-stain-
227 negative and facultative anaerobes. They were moderately halophilic, growing at 2-20
228 % (w/v) NaCl, with optimal growth at 7.5 % (w/v) NaCl; they were not able to grow in
229 the absence of NaCl. The temperature range for growth was 17-49 °C, with optimal
230 growth at 37 °C. The pH range for growth was at pH 5-10 and optimal growth was at
231 pH 7.2-7.4. Other morphological, physiological, biochemical and nutritional
232 characteristics of the strains are given in the species description and Supplementary
233 Table S2. The differential characteristics of these strains with respect to those of the
234 species and subspecies of the genus *Salinivibrio* are shown in Table 1.

235 *Phylogenetic analysis based on the 16S rRNA gene sequence*

236 The 16S rRNA gene sequence analysis showed that all isolated strains were
237 closely related to members of the genus *Salinivibrio*. The calculation of pairwise 16S
238 rRNA gene sequence similarities was achieved using the EzBioCloud tool [51],
239 showing 98.6-100 % similarity among the new strains. Additionally, according to the
240 EzBioCloud server, strains AL184^T, IB560, IB563, IC202, IC317, MA421, ML277,
241 ML318, ML328A and ML331 were most closely related to *S. sharmensis* DSM 18182^T
242 (99.6-98.2 % sequence similarity) and *S. costicola* subsp. *costicola* DSM 11403^T (99.0-
243 98.1 %). The 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity between the mentioned strains and the
244 type strains of species of other related genera was lower than 92.7 %. Phylogenetic

245 analysis using the neighbour-joining algorithm revealed that seven of the ten strains
246 form an independent lineage whereas three remaining strains form a monophyletic
247 group with the species *S. sharmensis* DSM 18182^T and *S. siamensis* JCM 14472^T (Fig.
248 1). In a previous study López-Hermoso et al. [27] concluded that the 16S rRNA gene is
249 not a good molecular marker for the delineation of species on the genus *Salinivibrio* and
250 they proposed the MLSA approach as alternative.

251 *Multilocus sequence analysis*

252 Concatenation of the sequences of the four (*gyrB*, *recA*, *rpoA* and *rpoD*) and
253 eight (*ftsZ*, *gapA*, *gyrB*, *mreB*, *pyrH*, *recA*, *rpoA* and *topA*) housekeeping genes yielded
254 an alignment of 2981 and 3817 nt, respectively. The resulting trees (Fig. 2 and
255 Supplementary Fig. S1) confirmed the taxonomic affiliation of the new strains to the
256 genus *Salinivibrio*, being most closely related to *S. siamensis* JCM 14472^T (96.8-95.4 %
257 based on four gene MLSA, and 94.9-94.7 % based on eight gene MLSA) and *S.*
258 *sharmensis* DSM 18182^T (94.0-92.6 % and 92.9-92.7 %, respectively). According to the
259 97 % cut-off value proposed by López-Hermoso et al. [27] these strains may constitute
260 a new species of the genus *Salinivibrio* (Supplementary Table S3). On the other hand,
261 the new strains constitute a separate phylogroup sharing concatenated similarity values
262 ranging from 99.9 to 96.9 % (four gene MLSA) and from 100 to 99.0 % (eight gene
263 MLSA) (Supplementary Table S3), which are above the cut-off value proposed by
264 López-Hermoso et al. [27] for species delineation within the genus *Salinivibrio*; thus,
265 according to this criterion this phylogroup constitutes a new species of this genus.

266 *G+C content and DNA–DNA hybridization*

267 The DNA G+C content of strains AL184^T, IB560, IB563, IC202, IC317,
268 MA421, ML277, ML318, ML328A and ML331, determined by the T_m method, was

269 estimated to be in the range 51.9 to 52.5 mol%; the DNA G+C content for strain
270 AL184⁴ was 52.5 mol% (Table S2). The DNA G+C content based on the drafts
271 genomes was in the range 50.2 to 50.9 mol%, with a value of 50.2 mol% for strain
272 AL184^T (Table S2). These percentages are close to the range described for members of
273 the genus *Salinivibrio* (49.0 to 51.0 mol%) (Table 1). The level of DNA–DNA
274 hybridization between strain AL184^T and strains IB560, IB563, IC202, IC317, MA421,
275 ML277, ML318, ML328A and ML331 was 75, 98, 98, 96, 95, 90, 100, 81 and 74 %,
276 respectively, indicating that the ten strains are members of the same species [45,46].
277 However, the percentage of DNA–DNA hybridization between strain AL184^T and *S.*
278 *sharmensis* DSM 18182^T, *S. costicola* subsp. *costicola* DSM 11403^T, *S. proteolyticus*
279 DSM 19052^T, *S. costicola* subsp. *alcaliphilus* DSM 16359^T, *S. costicola* subsp.
280 *vallismortis* DSM 8285^T and *S. siamensis* JCM 14472^T was 8, 17, 21, 28, 44, and 47 %,
281 respectively. These levels of DNA–DNA hybridization with respect to the type strains
282 of the phylogenetically most closely related species and subspecies of *Salinivibrio* are
283 significantly lower than the 70 % threshold value recommended for the delineation of
284 novel species [45,46]. These experimental data clearly show that the new isolates
285 constitute a new genospecies.

286 *Cellular fatty acid analysis*

287 The major fatty acids of strain AL184^T were C_{16:0} (23.7 %), C_{18:1} (14.2 %), C_{12:0}
288 (3.5 %), C_{18:0} (2.6 %) and C_{14:0} (2.1 %). This fatty acid composition is similar to those
289 of the type strains of the related species and subspecies of the genus *Salinivibrio*, being
290 C_{16:0} the most abundant fatty acid (Supplementary Table S4). This feature is in
291 agreement with previous studies on members of *Salinivibrio*, for which the predominant
292 fatty acids were always C_{16:0} and C_{18:1} [2,5,38,39].

293 *Whole-genome sequencing and ANI and GGDC calculations*

294 The mainly characteristic of the draft genomes of the ten new isolates have been
295 previously reported [26]. Comparison among the ten strains showed *in silico* GGDC
296 values higher than 70 % (80-100 %) (Table 2). According to Thompson *et al.* [48],
297 strains from the same species share 70 % or higher *in silico* GGDC values, confirming
298 the taxonomic position of the new strains as a single species. Values obtained from
299 OrthoANI and ANIb (100-97.7 % for both) (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S5) were
300 also consistent and above the proposed cut-off value for species boundary (95-96 %)
301 [37]. All OrthoANI and ANIb values between strains in the new phylogroup and the
302 existing taxa were higher than 95-96 %, thus supporting the proposal for a new species.
303 As expected, according to Lee *et al.* [24], OrthoANI percentages were slightly higher
304 than the ANIb values (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S5).

305 *Core genome phylogenetic reconstruction*

306 An all-versus-all BLAST protein-coding gene comparison indicated that the
307 pangenome of strains of the new phylogroup formed by the ten isolates and the closely
308 related species of the genus *Salinivibrio* comprised 6,041 genes. Of these, 1,230 genes
309 were shared by all strains (core orthologous genes), and phylogenetic reconstruction
310 based on their concatenated alignment revealed that the new phylogroup was well
311 separated from the rest of existing species and subspecies of the genus *Salinivibrio* (Fig.
312 3).

313 *Insights from the genome sequences*

314 The draft genomes of the ten strains of *Salinivibrio kushneri* sp. nov. ranged
315 from 3,3 to 3,6 Mbp (Supplementary Table S6), similarly to other *Salinivibrio* genomes
316 available in the public databases [12,26], with the exception of one of the two released

317 draft genomes of *S. costicola* subsp. *costicola*, which has 4,8 Mbp [7] probably due to a
318 misassembly. The sequenced genomes have quality enough, with N50 values equal or
319 higher than 21,208, contig number equal or lower to 236, almost 100 % completeness
320 and ≤ 0.72 % contamination (estimated using several markers as implemented in
321 CheckM software [35]) (Table 3). Among the most than 3,100 genes in each genome,
322 more than 72 % of the predicted protein-coding genes (CDS) were classified according
323 to functional categories, being the most representatives those related to the flagellum
324 (probably due to the motility by means of a polar flagellum characteristic of the strains
325 of this genus), RNA methylation, methionine biosynthesis, bacterial cytoskeleton,
326 serine-glyoxylate cycle, DNA repair and phosphate metabolism. All the *Salinivibrio*
327 *kushneri* genomes presented, at least, five rRNA operons (Table 3).

328 Genomes of the type strains of the *Salinivibrio* species are genetically coherent,
329 sharing 2,375 proteins (core orthologous proteins) (Fig. 4), while this number is
330 dramatically reduced to 1,893 core proteins when including the *Vibrio cholerae* N16961
331 genome into the analysis. Since there is a large number of proteins common to
332 *Salinivibrio* representatives that are not present in *V. cholerae*, we could expect that the
333 latter possessed a large amount of unique proteins which could not be identified in
334 *Salinivibrio*. Surprisingly, only 19 proteins were specific of *V. cholerae*, while the
335 *Salinivibrio* genomes contained up to 113 unique proteins. When considering just the
336 five type strains of the genus, *S. costicola* subsp. *costicola* possessed the higher number
337 of exclusive proteins (149), followed by *S. proteolyticus* (121). The new proposed
338 species, *S. kushneri* also contained a considerable number of unique proteins (59) (Fig.
339 4).

340 **Conclusion**

341 Results obtained from this polyphasic taxonomic study, including the
342 phylogenetic analyses, DDH, ANI, GGDC, core-genome, chemotaxonomic analysis and
343 phenotypic tests demonstrated that the ten strains investigated constitute a novel species
344 within the genus *Salinivibrio*, for which the name *Salinivibrio kushneri* sp. nov. is
345 proposed, with strain AL184^T (= CECT 9177^T = LMG 29817^T) designated as the type
346 strain.

347 **Description of *Salinivibrio kushneri* sp. nov.**

348 *Salinivibrio kushneri* (kush'ner.i. N.L. gen. n. of Kushner, in honour of Professor Donn
349 J. Kushner, for his pioneer work and his contributions to halophile microbiology).

350 Cells are Gram-stain-negative; non-endospore-forming, motile singly curved
351 rods, 0.5 x 2.5-3.2 µm. Colonies on SW medium are circular, with entire edges, bright,
352 and creamy-pigmented (0.9–2.1 mm). Facultative anaerobic. Grows at 17-49 °C
353 (optimally at 37 °C), at pH values of 5-10 (optimally at pH 7.2-7.4). Moderately
354 halophilic, growing at 2-20 % (w/v) NaCl (optimally at 7.5 %, w/v NaCl). No growth
355 occurred in the absence of sodium chloride in the culture media. KCl cannot substitute
356 NaCl. Positive for catalase, oxidase, nitrate reduction, Voges-Proskauer, phosphatase
357 and hydrolysis of DNA. Negative for the hydrolysis of Tween 80, methyl red test and
358 nitrite reduction. Most strains are able to hydrolyze casein and gelatin, while most
359 strains are not able to hydrolyze aesculin or starch. Acid is produced from fructose, D-
360 glucose, maltose, ribose and D-trehalose, but not from aesculin, lactose, raffinose and
361 D-xylose. Production of indole is generally negative. Ribose and sucrose are utilized as
362 sole carbon and energy source, and alanine is used as sole carbon, nitrogen and energy
363 source. Utilization of D-trehalose and glutamine are positive for most strains as sole
364 source of carbon and energy or carbon, nitrogen and energy, respectively. C_{16:0} and C_{18:1}
365 are the predominant cellular fatty acids. The DNA G+C content range is: 50.2-50.9

366 mol% (genome) and 51.9-52.5 mol% (T_m). The estimated genome size is 3.3-3.6 Mb.
367 Isolated from marine salterns.

368 The type strain is AL184^T (= CECT 9177^T = LMG 29817^T), isolated from water
369 pond of a solar saltern in Santa Pola, Alicante, Spain. The DNA G+C content of the
370 type strain is 50.2 mol% (genome) and 52.5 mol % (T_m). Strains IB560, IB563, IC202,
371 IC317, MA421, ML277, ML318, ML328A and ML331 are additional strains of the
372 species. The Digital Protologue taxonumber is TA00236.

373

374

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382

383 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

384 Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online
385 version at XXXXXX.

386

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539 **Legends of figures**

540

541 **Fig. 1.** Neighbour-joining tree based on the 16S rRNA gene sequence comparison,
542 showing the phylogenetic position of strains AL184^T, IB560, IB563, IC202, IC317,
543 MA421, ML277, ML318, ML328A and ML331 and their relationship with other
544 species and subspecies of the genus *Salinivibrio*. The GenBank/EMBL/DDBJ accession
545 number of each sequence is shown in parenthesis. Filled circles indicate nodes that were
546 also obtained in maximum-parsimony and maximum-likelihood trees based on the same
547 sequences. Bootstrap values over 70 % are shown at the nodes. Bar, 0.01 substitutions
548 per nucleotide position. The species *Vibrio cholerae* CECT 514^T was used as outgroup.

549

550

551 **Fig. 2.** Neighbour-joining tree based on the concatenated *gyrB*, *recA*, *rpoA* and *rpoD*
552 gene sequence comparison, showing the phylogenetic position of strains AL184^T,
553 IB560, IB563, IC202, IC317, MA421, ML277, ML318, ML328A and ML331 and their
554 relationship with other species and subspecies of the genus *Salinivibrio*. Filled circles
555 indicate nodes that were also obtained in maximum-parsimony and maximum-
556 likelihood trees based on the same sequences. Bootstrap values over 70 % are shown at
557 the nodes. Bar, 0.05 substitutions per nucleotide position. The species *Vibrio cholerae*
558 N16961 was used as outgroup.

559

560

561 **Fig. 3.** Core phylogenomic tree of the 16 available genomes of the genus *Salinivibrio*.

562 This tree was constructed based on the neighbour-joining distance calculated from the

563 alignment of 1,230 shared orthologous genes of these genomes. All genomes were

564 sequenced by López-Hermoso et al. [26] and Gorriti et al. [12]. Filled circles indicate

565 nodes that were also obtained in maximum-parsimony and maximum-likelihood trees

566 based on the same sequences. Bootstrap values over 70 % are shown above the branch.

567 Bar, 0.01 substitutions per nucleotide position. The species *Vibrio cholerae* N16961

568 was used as outgroup.

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570

571 **Fig. 4.** Venn diagram showing the core orthologous and unique proteins for the type

572 strains of species of the genus *Salinivibrio*.

573 **Table 1.** Differential characteristics between *Salinivibrio kushneri* sp. nov. and related
 574 species and subspecies of the genus *Salinivibrio*.

575 1, *Salinivibrio kushneri* sp. nov. (10 strains); 2, *S. siamensis* JCM 14472^T; 3, *S. sharmensis*
 576 DSM 18182^T; 4, *S. costicola* subsp. *alcaliphilus* DSM 16359^T; 5, *S. costicola* subsp. *costicola*
 577 DSM 11403^T; 6, *S. proteolyticus* DSM 19052^T; 7, *S. costicola* subsp. *vallismortis* DSM 8285^T.
 578 All strains were curve rods. They were positive for catalase, oxidase, hydrolysis of DNA,
 579 Voges-Proskauer and phosphatase, and utilization of ribose as sole carbon and energy source.
 580 All strains produced acid from fructose, D-glucose, maltose and D-trehalose. All strains were
 581 negative for acid production from lactose, raffinose and D-xylose. All data are from this study
 582 unless otherwise indicated. +, positive, -, negative.

Characteristic	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Colony pigmentation	Cream	Cream ^a	Cream ^b	Cream-pink ^c	Cream ^d	Cream-white ^e	Cream-white ^f
NaCl range (% w/v)	2-20	1-22 ^a	6-16 ^b	2-25 ^c	0.5-20 ^d	1-17 ^e	0-12.5 ^f
NaCl optimum (% w/v)	7.5	10 ^a	10 ^b	10 ^c	10 ^d	5 ^e	2.5 ^f
Temperature range (°C)	17-49	10-47 ^a	25-40 ^b	10-40 ^c	5-45 ^d	10-45 ^e	20-50 ^f
Temperature optimum (°C)	37	37 ^a	35 ^b	30 ^c	37 ^d	35 ^e	37 ^f
pH range	5-10	5-9 ^a	6-10 ^b	7-10.5 ^c	5-10 ^d	5-9.5 ^e	5-10 ^f
pH optimum	7.2-7.4	8 ^a	9 ^b	9 ^c	7.5 ^d	8 ^e	7.3 ^f
Anaerobic growth	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
Nitrate reduction	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
Nitrite reduction	-	-	-	+	-	+	-
Hydrolysis of Tween 80	-	+	-	-	-	-	+
Acid production from ribose	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
Utilization of sucrose as sole carbon and energy source	+	-	-	+	+	+	+
Utilization of alanine as sole carbon, nitrogen	+	+	+	+	+	-	-

Characteristic	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
and energy source							
DNA G+C content (<i>T_m</i>) (mol%)	51.9-52.5	49.0 ^a	51.0 ^b	49.3 ^c	50.0 ^d	49.5 ^e	50.0 ^f
DNA G+C content (genome) (mol%)	50.2-50.9	50.3	50.4	49.1	49.2	49.8	49.7

583

584 ^a Data taken from Chamroensaksri et al. [5].

585 ^b Data taken from Romano et al. [39].

586 ^c Data taken from Romano et al. [38].

587 ^d Data taken from Mellado et al. [31].

588 ^e Data taken from Amoozegar et al. [2].

589 ^f Data taken from Huang et al. [16].

590

591 **Table 2.** OrthoANI (upper triangle in bold) and GGDC (lower triangle) values among
 592 the genomes of the ten strains of *Salinivibrio kushneri* and the type strains of the species
 593 and subspecies of the genus *Salinivibrio*.

Strain	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. <i>S. kushneri</i> AL184 ^T	100	98.4	98.2	98.2	98.4	98.1	98.3	98.4	97.7	98.3
2. <i>S. kushneri</i> IB560	84.7	100	98.4	98.2	98.2	98.4	98.1	98.3	98.4	97.7
3. <i>S. kushneri</i> IB563	83.3	81.9	100	99.4	98.2	97.8	98.1	98.2	98.2	98.1
4. <i>S. kushneri</i> IC202	85.4	81.7	95.6	100	98.2	97.8	98.1	98.1	98.2	98.0
5. <i>S. kushneri</i> IC317	85.8	85.0	83.4	83.0	100	98.1	98.3	99.9	99.4	98.4
6. <i>S. kushneri</i> MA421	83.0	82.4	80.3	80.0	83.1	100	98.5	98.2	98.1	97.9
7. <i>S. kushneri</i> ML277	85.0	84.5	82.4	82.1	83.5	86.7	100	98.4	98.3	98.2
8. <i>S. kushneri</i> ML318	86.0	85.0	83.3	83.1	99.7	83.1	85.4	100	98.2	98.3
9. <i>S. kushneri</i> ML328A	86.0	87.5	83.7	83.2	95.7	83.8	85.2	95.9	100	98.3
10. <i>S. kushneri</i> ML331	85.7	84.0	83.2	82.3	85.3	81.8	84.3	85.5	85.1	100
11. <i>S. costicola</i> subsp. <i>alcaliphilus</i> DSM 16359 ^T	81.9 24.5	81.9 24.5	82.0 24.9	81.9 24.8	81.9 24.7	81.9 24.7	81.8 24.6	81.8 24.5	81.8 24.5	82.0 24.4
12. <i>S. costicola</i> subsp. <i>costicola</i> LMG 11651 ^T	81.8 24.5	81.7 24.6	82.2 25.1	82.0 25.1	81.8 24.8	81.8 24.7	81.9 24.7	81.8 24.5	82.0 24.5	81.8 24.6
13. <i>S. costicola</i> subsp. <i>vallismortis</i> DSM 8285 ^T	80.4 23.7	80.5 23.5	80.5 23.5	80.2 23.5	80.6 24.0	80.5 23.4	80.5 23.3	80.5 23.6	80.3 23.5	80.6 23.7
14. <i>S. proteolyticus</i> DSM 19052 ^T	80.7 23.6	80.5 23.5	80.4 23.6	80.5 23.6	80.6 24.0	80.5 23.5	80.4 24.4	80.5 23.6	80.6 23.5	80.8 23.6
15. <i>S. sharmensis</i> DSM 18182 ^T	91.1 42.7	91.1 42.9	91.0 42.6	90.9 42.6	91.3 42.9	91.0 43.0	91.2 43.0	91.1 42.9	91.0 42.8	91.1 42.8
16. <i>S. siamensis</i> JCM 14472 ^T	91.6 44.5	91.8 44.8	91.6 44.6	91.6 44.6	91.6 44.6	91.8 45.0	91.7 44.8	91.6 44.6	91.5 44.5	91.5 44.6

594

595 **Figure 1**

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599 **Figure 2**

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603 **Figure 3**

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608 **Figure 4**

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